

weedings and in the unweeded check.

Pendimethalin at 1.25 kg/ ha and thiobencarb at 1.50 kg/ha followed by hand weeding gave highest grain yields (see table).

Weeding cost was highest with the peg-type weeder. The marginal benefit-cost ratio was highest with the combination of thiobencarb at 1.00 kg/ha followed by 2,4-D EE. □

Effect of weed control treatments on major weed, total weed dry matter, and grain yield in upland banded rice. Tirunelveli, India, 1984-85.

Treatment ^a	Rate (kg/ha)	<i>Eragrostis japonica</i> (no. m ²) 80 DAS	Total weed dry matter (kg/ha) 80 DAS	Grain yield (t/ha)	Weeding cost (\$/ha)	Benefit: cost ratio
Pendimethalin fb HW 30 DAS	1.25	12.6	61.5	3.1	48.6	6.03
Thiobencarb fb HW 30 DAS	1.5	15.8	69.5	3.0	31.4	7.50
Hand weeding at 20, 35, and 50 DAS	—	19.8	75.9	2.8	63.8	3.65
Working peg-type weeder at 20, 35, and 50 DAS	at	-25.7	185.4	2.6	82.2	2.16
Thiobencarb fb post-em	1.0					
2,4-D EE 35 DAS	0.5	28.5	206.6	2.6	24.3	9.34
Pendimethalin fb HW 30 DAS	0.75	33.6	277.5	2.5	41.1	4.76
Thiobencarb fb HW at 30 and 50 DAS	1.0	30.3	227.6	2.5	51.7	3.73
Pendimethalin fb HW at 30 and 50 DAS	0.75	31.6	221.3	2.5	56.2	3.41
Thiobencarb fb HW 30 DAS	1.0	36.6	265.6	2.4	37.0	5.28
Pendimethalin fb post-em	0.75					
2,4D EE 35 DAS	0.5	26.4	208.7	2.4	30.1	6.86
Hand weeding at 20 and 35 DAS	—	106.3	117.3	2.2	48.0	2.97
Unweeded check	—	252.6	1354.5	0.4	—	—
CD (P = 0.05)		3.9	65.9	1.5	—	—

^a Pre-em = preemergence, post-em = postemergence, fb = followed by, HW = hand weeding. Men labor at US\$0.8/8 h and women at US\$0.6/8 h. Pendimethalin cost, US\$8.0/liter; thiobencarb, US\$7.1/liter; 2,4-D EE, US\$4.0/liter.

Weeds in shifting cultivation in Quezon Province, Philippines

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In Real, Quezon Province, farmers plant rice at the start of the rainy season immediately after clearing secondary forests by dibbling into fields that have had no land

preparation. After the rice is harvested, citrus or sweet potato is planted, depending on the availability of citrus seedlings.

In 1984, we surveyed 4 recently cleared fields 19, 69, and 76 d after seeding (DAS) rice. At the same time, we surveyed adjacent areas planted to citrus and sweet potato which had been cleared the previous year.

Percentage of weed cover and weed

Weeds growing in association with rice, citrus, and sweet potato in Real, Quezon, Philippines, Jul-Sep 1984.

Weed species	Rice		Citrus	Sweet potato
	Sloping land	Flat land		
<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>	✓	—	—	✓
<i>Axonopus compressus</i>	✓	✓	—	—
<i>Blumea sinuata</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>Crassocephalum crepidioides</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>Cyperus halpan</i>	—	✓	—	—
<i>Emilia sonchifolia</i>	—	—	✓	✓
<i>Imperata cylindrica</i>	✓	✓	—	—
<i>Paspalum conjugatum</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>Pseudoelephantopus spicatus</i>	—	✓	—	—
<i>Solanum eumingii</i>	✓	✓	—	—

species were recorded.

None of the crops were weeded. In recently cleared areas where the land was sloping, weeds were not a problem. Weed cover was 0-3% at 19 DAS and 0-15% at 69-76 DAS. In one field, 10% was flat land adjacent to a stream. The soil was moist most of the time, which favored weed seed germination and growth. Weed cover in this area ranged from 30% at 19 DAS to 90% at 76 DAS.

Where clearing had been done the previous year, weed infestation was severe, particularly in the area planted to citrus where weed cover was 98%. *Paspalum conjugatum*, the predominant weed, covered 95% of the area. Sweet potato suppressed weed growth; weed cover in that field was only 30%.

Weeds growing in association with the different crops are listed in the table. *P. conjugatum* was the predominant weed in all fields. It is expected that *P. conjugatum* and *Imperata cylindrica*, which are aggressive species, will provide most of the weed cover in future years in fields currently planted to rice.

To our knowledge, this is the first time *Axonopus compressus* and *Solanum eumingii* have been reported as weeds of rice in the Philippines. □

Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

Golden apple snail: a pest of rice

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The golden apple snail *Pomacea canaliculata*, an aquatic gastropod originating from South America, was introduced recently in the Philippines as a culture material to be farmed in

cement tanks, ponds, or other controlled environments.

In recent surveys, the snail and its egg masses (Fig. 1a) were found in abundance in the *Azolla* propagation ponds of the U.P. College of Agriculture at Los Baños (Fig. 1b) and in adjoining irrigated ricefields on the IRRI experimental farm. The snail feeds voraciously on *Azolla*. Adults measuring 22-26 mm can consume up to 15 g of *Azolla* fronds in 12-24 h.

The snail feeds also on other succulent aquatic vegetation, such as newly transplanted rice. It attacks the base of rice seedlings and then devours aerial parts. A large snail can consume a blade of rice in 3-5 min (Fig. 1c). The snail is most active at dusk, night, and dawn.

Damage is most severe in low-lying portions of newly transplanted ricefields. Severely damaged plots are characterized by missing seedlings and floating, cut leaves (Fig. 1d). Damage can reach 10-20%. In a freshly transplanted 0.1-ha ricefield on the IRRI farm where damage was observed, three 3-gallon pails of golden apple snails were collected.

Females start laying eggs at 75-90 d, preferably on substrates protruding above the water surface (rice hills, weeds, rat fence walls, and bamboo stakes). A single gravid female can lay 25-320 bright pink eggs per week. Eggs hatch in 8-15 d, depending upon temperature.

Newly hatched snail larvae about 2 mm in diameter readily disperse

1. Golden apple snail: a) females and their egg masses on rice plants; b) clusters of egg masses on bamboo stakes in an *Azolla* propagation pond; c) full-grown snail grazing on a rice seedling; d) missing seedlings due to feeding by full-grown snails.

through irrigation water to other ricefields. Young snails feed on algae. Older snails have a horny tongue or radula with rows upon rows of sharp teeth (Fig. 2). The snails are more active and grow faster during warmer months, but mortality is high under hot temperatures.

The golden apple snail can be controlled with organotin molluscicides. However, these chemicals are also toxic to aquatic animals such as fish and tadpoles. Manual collection of snail egg masses can alleviate the problem in ricefields. □

2. Radular tooth pattern of the golden apple snail.

Irrigation Water Management

The effect of supplementary irrigation on rice yield in Bangladesh

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In Bangladesh, rice is grown in aus (summer), aman (autumn), and boro (winter). Although aus and aman rice cover 89% of the total cropped area and yield 84% of the total rice output, they are still grown as rainfed crops. Uncertain rainfall during transplanting

and critical growth periods means crop losses, even though 80% of the mean annual rainfall in the country (1,400 mm in the northwest to over 5,000 mm in the northeast) occurs during aus and aman.

We studied the amount of